
UNEMPLOYMENT AND CAPITALISTS EXPLOITATION OF YOUNG GRADUATES: NIGERIA IN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Unemployment particularly young graduate unemployment is a major development problem in Nigeria. A global threat to the achievement of the Nigeria's sustainable development goals. It impedes the fight to end poverty in all its forms, limits opportunities to promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth, and undermines Nigeria's ability to reduce inequalities. It is worrying that unemployment continues to grow despite major interventions. It is argued in the paper that graduates unemployment is potentially dangerous as it sends disturbing signal to all segments of the Nigerian Society. The rate of graduates unemployment in Nigeria is high, even at the period of economic normalcy i.e. the oil boom of the 1970s (6.2%); 1980s (9.8%) and the 1990s (11.5%). Graduates unemployment therefore is not a recent phenomenon as is conveyed in this study. This paper relied on secondary sources of data, and the Marxist approach as its framework of analysis to argue that ignoring the political, economic and social roles young graduates play in a society amounts to threatening the very survival of that society, Nigeria as a case in-point. Thus to reduce unemployment, the paper recommends among others, the establishment of Work Incentive Program (WIN) by the Nigerian State, as it's done in the capitalist America Government in league with the private sector. The paper further sees hope for Nigeria only if graduates are mobilized by way of genuinely socializing them into taking their roles in the stratification system and help youth empowerment institutions address the gaps in strategies for directing youths to generating income.

Keywords: Unemployment, Graduates, Capitalism, Exploitation, Capital exploitation

Introduction

Unemployment is one of the fundamental developmental challenges facing Nigeria at the moment. Research have shown that unemployment was high in the 1980s, but the available-local and international bodies, and the glaring evidence of joblessness in this decades are clear indications that there was no time in Nigeria's chequered history where unemployment is as serious as now. Thus in spite of her abundant human and natural resources, Nigeria remains a poor country with 70% of her population living below poverty line in both rural and urban areas (Ali-Akpajiak and Pyke 2003:6).

Studies such as Folayan (1979), Fajana (2000), Diejomaoh (1979) show that unemployment in Nigeria was not a serious problem before and after the civil war (1967-1970). What was noticeable as at then was a temporarily gap between searching for job by graduates and processing job applications by employers. Medical doctors, engineers, lawyers, economists, accountants, lecturers etc were in short supply. There was shortage of skilled manpower. Expatriates were taken to fill some technical and professional jobs, (Civil Service Report, 1981; 1982). However, the trend has changed greatly from the late 1970s till date with the establishment of private universities, more federal universities, and polytechnics to satisfy the nation's education aspirations. The numbers of universities and polytechnics have grossly increased to 107 universities in 2012, over 260 in 2024, and also the Polytechnics to 92 in 2021 and 124 in 2024 and their curriculum expanded.

There is a lag in production and the resulting output in the economy; consequently, there is the need for strong institutional, organizational and economic structures to complement Nigeria's rich natural resources. The enrollment and turn-out of graduates have exploded annually without corresponding changes in the structure of the Nigerian economy. Explosion in the number of higher institutions and the turn-out of graduates is not peculiar to Nigeria.

In most countries of the world, throughout the 20th century, rapid growth in the 1920s was followed by a decade of stagnation in the 1930s. Growth resumed after the Second World War and accelerated in the 1960s and early 1970s. There was a decade and a half of stagnation in the late 1970s, and 1980s, followed by more fast growth in the 1990s and the early of the 21st century. High growth rates in higher education result in rapidly increasing number of graduates trying to find jobs

For every graduate, finding a decent job is a milestone towards self-reliance, and contributing to poverty reduction, social stability and sustainable development. One would have assumed that graduates stand a better chance to be gainfully employed than people with secondary school education. However, the growing rate of graduate unemployment puts a big question mark on the economy and the education system.

This situation is sad to hear of a country that is blessed with a lot of human and natural resources capable of providing employment for the teeming young graduates, despite recent improvements in Nigeria economic growth, graduates unemployment remains a great challenge to policymakers, graduates empowerment agents, and investors (Alfonsi et al.,

2020).

The high graduate's unemployment rate in Nigeria is of great concern and warrants urgent solutions (Maulani & Agwanda, 2020). It is in the light of the above exposition that this paper unemployment and capitalist exploitation of graduates are recent phenomenon in Nigeria, this paper undertakes a historic examination of unemployment and capitalist exploitation of young graduates

Literature Review

In this section, we reviewed relevant and related literature

Unemployment

There seems to be a consensus on the definitions and usage of the concept, unemployment. According to Udu and Agu (2005), unemployment is "a situation in which persons capable and willing to work are unable to find suitable paid employment". As defined by International Labour Organization (2007), unemployed workers are those who are currently not working but are willing and able to work for pay, currently available to work and have actively search for work. Hornby (2010) defines unemployment as "the facts of a number of people not having a job; the number of people without a job; the state of not having a job". In the same vein, an operational definition of unemployment for this work will include the underemployed, hence unemployment occurs when people who are able and willing to work are without jobs, or cannot find work that is effective and productive to do. It also occurs when people undertake jobs that are contrary or lower than their academic qualifications or areas of specialization. For instance, a first or second degree holder that enrolled as a recruit into any of the armed forces of paramilitary or a degree holder working as a clerk in an office is greatly underutilized and as such could be termed as unemployed even when such person on a job. According to .C. B. Mamoria, unemployment is a state of worklessness for a man fit and willing to work ,that is, it is a condition of involuntary and not voluntary idleness.

Exploitation

Traditionally, exploitation is taking advantage of someone or something so that you can profit from it. From an economic perspective, nearly everything, whether people or the earth, can be exploited. Exploitation is when someone sees an opportunity to improve themselves by unfairly using someone else's work. According to Joan Robinson (2006: 45)

According to Karl Marx Exploitation involves an unfair relationship, in which one party benefits at the expense of another. Due to this unfairness, exploitation is a highly emotive concept, involving value judgments from different perspectives. Recruitment exercises conducted by many public and private organizations in Nigeria showcase the level of exploitation faced by Nigerian graduates who are seeking for jobs. No doubt, Nigeria has a high graduates unemployment level and few employment opportunities exist for the innumerable qualified citizens who seek them daily. Above the scenario has engendered exploiters who take advantage of the desperation and helplessness of Nigerian graduates who are seeking for jobs. They demand registration fees from graduates promising them

employment with their clients (employers). Where a job is secured, it is usually agreed between the centre and the employer for the fresh employee to forfeit one or two month's salary to the centre as fee for its services.

Types of Exploitation

Exploitation can be transactional or structural. In the former case, the unfairness is a property of a discrete transaction between two or more individuals. A sweatshop that pays low wages, for example, or a pharmaceutical research firm that tests drugs on poor subjects in the developing world, might be said to exploit others in this sense. But exploitation can also be structural—a property of institutions or systems in which the “rules of the game” unfairly benefit one group of people to the detriment of another. As we will see below, Karl Marx believed that the economic and political institutions of capitalism were exploitative in this sense. And some contemporary feminists have argued that the institution of traditional marriage is exploitative insofar as it preys upon and reinforces pernicious forms of inequality between men and women (Sample 2003:4).

Exploitation can also be harmful or mutually beneficial. Harmful exploitation involves an interaction that leaves the victim worse off than she was, and than she was entitled to be. The sort of exploitation involved in coercive sex trafficking, for instance, is harmful in this sense. But as we will see below, not all exploitation is harmful. Exploitation can also be mutually beneficial, where both parties walk away better off than they were *ex ante*. Most philosophers think that what makes such mutually beneficial interactions nevertheless exploitative is that they are, in some way, unfair.

It is relatively easy to come up with intuitively compelling cases of unfair, exploitative behavior. Providing a philosophical analysis to support and develop those intuitions, however, has proven more difficult. The most obvious difficulty is specifying the conditions under which a transaction or institution may be said to be unfair. Does the unfairness involved in exploitation relate to the distribution of resources? Or a violation of her moral rights? Is the unfairness involved in exploitation a matter of procedure, substance, or both? And how, if at all, are the attitudes and motives of the would-be exploiter relevant to assessing charges of exploitation

Theoretical Framework

There remain divergent theoretical debates among economists and theorists regarding the issue of unemployment. However, the Marxist approach is applied in this paper to discuss the multidimensional situation of graduates' unemployment in Nigeria.

In some of his early works, Marx suggests that the poverty of the graduates goes hand in hand with capitalist production. For example, in "Alienated Labor" he claims that in capitalist society, "labor produces marvels for the wealthy but it produces deprivation for the graduates. Indeed, "so much does the realization of labor appear as diminution of the graduate that the graduates are diminished to the point of starvation".

This view, that as a necessary result of the capitalist mode of production the average graduate is deprived of many of the necessities of life, is one that Marx had abandoned by the time he wrote *Capital*. In *Capital*, Marx suggests that it is not part of the "inner essence" of capitalist exploitation that the graduates be deprived of the necessities of life. To the contrary, the reproduction of the capitalist mode of production requires the reproduction of the class of graduates which in turn requires providing the graduate with the necessities of life.

According to Marx, understanding the nature of capitalist exploitation involves "recognizing the inner essence and inner structure" of capitalism as well as the relationship between the inner essence and its "outer appearance" (*Capital* 3: 168). Let the ideal capitalist society denote the (impossible) capitalist society in which inner essence and outer appearance coincide. Marx describes the ideal capitalist society as one in which all production takes the form of commodity production. Commodity production is the production of use-values or "useful things" (*Capital* 1: 36), not for the sake of consumption or use, but rather for the sake of exchange. Commodity production is therefore also the production of exchangeable things or "depositories is that required to produce [it] under the normal conditions of production, and with the average degree of skill and intensity prevalent at the time" According to Marx, in an ideal capitalist society things exchange at their values — "equivalent [is] exchanged for equivalent" In other words, given a universally accepted equivalent or money-commodity, the prices of commodities are proportional to their values

Cause of Graduates Unemployment

This study singles out the graduate unemployment in Nigeria for critical analysis and emphasis on the economic implications Many studies have focused on unemployment (Dabalén and Adekoka, 2000), youth unemployment (Uwem and Ndem, 2012), higher education and the demand for manpower (Ugwonah and Omeje, 1998), Labor Unemployment causes premature death resulting from criminality, incapacitation, stroke, hypertension, malnutrition, diabetes, vehicular accidents and all the tragedies associated with poverty. Facing the pressure to earn income and survival, the unemployed engages in risky and sometimes immoral jobs. Besides, poor quality of graduates is partly due to poor funding of education and low number of qualified teachers. Most of the best brains leave the country to Europe, North America, and East Asia for these reasons. After completing their postgraduate studies in these continents, they remain there on paid jobs. They do not return home to give back to their own system. Brain drain or human capital flight becomes a cause of unemployment and also a result of unemployment.

Ogundeowole (2002) attributes graduates unemployment in Nigeria to bad government. Unemployment in Nigeria has caused wide rural-urban migration, worsening the disparities between the two regions. The population of idlers in Lagos, Abuja, Kano, Calabar, Port Harcourt etc is alarming. The unemployed graduates migrate to these cities with the hope of getting jobs; since the economic and social structures in their various hometowns are poor, 5-6 years later; they still do not find decent jobs 20% of the graduates interviewed have very poor, old parents who have invested their life savings to see their ward through graduation, hoping that the young graduate would find a decent job and assume responsibility over the family. 30%

of the graduates got married before or during the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC). Bearing children before finding a job increases their social and economic responsibilities, thus increasing the burden of unemployment.

Corruption is not a strange word to an average Nigerian. Simply put, it is a dishonest or illegal behavior, especially of people in authority. It is an abuse of public office for private gain which usually involves embezzlement of public funds, nepotism and falsification of facts and figures, etc. Corruption has no doubt done incalculable damages to every facets of the country Nigeria. It has undermines democratic institutions, retarded economic growth and development (Samuel, 2011); and cause poverty in the mist of plenty, it has prevented the country from making political, social and economic progress and ultimately brought about high level of

The overriding concern is how to grow output and reduce graduates unemployment. Amidst the tight unemployment market, employers are demanding for several years of working experience from fresh graduates or potential candidates. While the fresh graduates need the job to gain experience, employers need the experience to give the job. However, the Nigerian government in 2012, has introduced Employment Tax Relief (ETR, 2012), where companies income tax (exemption of profits) order, 2012 for any company with a minimum net employment of 10 employees of which 60% are employees without any form of previous experience after graduating from school. The major hope for the economy at the moment is policy support aimed at stimulating growth in the non-oil sector in recent times. Of the major problems is the uneven distribution of infrastructure between the urban and regional geography, such that graduates are not motivated to stay in the villages and rural areas and to be self-reliance. They all migrate to the cities in search of white-collar jobs. Many graduates consider agriculture as an inferior source for gainful, long term employment. Urban unemployment is worse than the regions, because after completing their compulsory one year National Youth Service Scheme (NYSC), the graduates are crowded, jobless in the urban squalor. This has created multiple socio-economic problems in the cities and the regions, very vulnerable to criminality. Unemployment has severe social, economic and psychological consequences on the graduates, their families and the nation. After the graduates have failed to find suitable jobs to their qualifications and training, they resort to any kind of job in the informal sector.

Young Graduates and Job Exploitation in Nigeria

Mark & Obi (2022) recognized several factors that make a state hostile and unsafe; In Nigeria for instance, they identified unemployment, poverty, drug abuse, greed, quest to get rich quick among others as causes of insecurity. They noted that unemployment as the cause of Poverty, and its alleviation efforts in Nigeria have been pursued through the application of orthodox capitalist strategies. For instance, In 2008, the Nigerian Immigration Service conducted a recruitment exercise; young graduates were required to buy internet scratch cards, apply online, buy sports kith, undergo medical tests and fitness exercises, etc. Not only did applicants spend much money in the process, some of them reportedly lost their lives as a result of the fitness exercise. The same year, the Nigerian Police Force and its consultants made every applicant to buy a N2, 000 internet scratch card, apply online and incur other expenses for recruitment into the Force.

Impact of Graduates Unemployment on Nigeria Economy

An economy with high graduates unemployed is not using all of the resources, specifically labour available to it. Since it is operating below its production possibility frontier, it could have higher output if the entire workforce were utilized.

If as a result of lack of jobs, the frictionally unemployed graduates accept and work below capacity (i.e. underemployment), and operate below their skill level, it reducing the economy's efficiency. It leads to loss of potential output in a developing economy. More so, during a long period of unemployment, workers can also lose their skills, causing a loss of human capital. It could also lead to low level of income and high rate of income inequality which further aggravates the high rate of poverty and graduate unemployment with its attendance consequence.

One of the major implications of high graduate unemployment to a country like Nigeria with wide spread corruption and bad governance, is palpable, increase apathy, cynicism and despondency. Many people become increasingly individualistic and exclusively preoccupied with the problem of survival and subsistence. They show little or no concern for government issues, activities and policies and programs

High graduate unemployment has been blamed for civil unrest in Nigeria, in some cases leading to revolution e.g. Boko Haram crisis in the Northern part of the country. It was one of the thematic causes of the mass-protest in Egypt that over-thrown president Hosni Mubarak on 11th February, 2011, leading to the current state of anarchy. Hassan (2010) believes that the high rate of kidnapping, civil unrest and political thuggery can be traced to graduates unemployment situation in Nigeria.

Efforts to Curb Graduates Unemployment in Nigeria

In Nigeria, unemployment rate has been found to be highly based on lack of entrepreneurial development. This justifies the need to increase entrepreneurial activities to reduce high rate of unemployment and its negative effects. Opportunities exist in the agricultural sector which is Africa's comparative advantage. Many of the graduates in related fields can be encouraged with soft loans to go into fish farming, cattle rearing, mushroom farming, bee/honey farming, cassava farming and processing, rabbit farming, poultry, rice farming etc all in commercial quantity, well packaged for domestic consumption and exports. 90% of the graduates (for OND, HND, Bachelor, and Masters Degrees) are youths in the age bracket 20-35 years. They are active, with vigor, and the energy to contribute to national productivity.

More so, some intervention programs introduced in Nigeria such as the Nigerian Directorate of Employment (NDE) with the goal of designing and implementing programs to combat mass unemployment, Poverty Alleviation Programs (PAPs), Subsidy Re- investment Program (SURE-P), YOUWIN program, etc, and subsequent injection of billions of naira into these programs and other sectors to create more employment opportunities as claimed by the Federal Government can be seen as a leap into the Marxist theory.

Measures to Combat problems of Young Graduates and Job Exploitation

The first three National Development Plans indirectly attempted to deal with reduction of

capitalist exploitation of graduates through the pursuit of economic growth. The fourth development plan attempted to curtail the level of capitalist exploitation of graduates through, “The increase in the real income of the average citizen, even distribution of income among individuals and socio-economic groups”.

In addition, government had on many occasions taken calculated steps to combat capitalist exploitation of graduates through institution building. Some of these institutions include local government, banking institutions, and government ministries. However, rather than mitigate the situation, the application of these capitalist strategies has worsened the level of unemployment and brought about poverty. Some bourgeois scholars contended that the most crucial factor that accounts for the persistence of low levels of living, rising unemployment, and growing income inequality in the Third World is the highly asymmetrical distribution of economic and political power between the rich and poor countries. This makes the rich nations to not only control the pattern of international trade but also to dictate the terms whereby technology, foreign aid, and private capital are transferred to developing countries. Given the highly unequal distribution of world resources between the North and the South, it is not surprising that the economies of the latter cannot be resilience and self-reliant. Under this situation poverty alleviation is untenable and cannot be sustained

Another problem with the capitalist exploitation of graduates is that it makes the economies of Third World countries in general, especially Nigeria in particular, to be externally oriented. This inhibits the development efforts of the poor nations. According to Todaro & Smith (2004), this has been manifested through the transfer of developed world values, attitudes, institutions and standards of behavior to poor countries. For instance the transfer of inappropriate educational structures, curricular, school system, and the organization and orientation of health services in accordance with the curative rather than preventive model; and the importation of inappropriate structures and procedures for public bureaucratic and administrative system.

Another fundamental problem of capitalist exploitation of graduates with respect to poverty reduction is that it enhances the deterioration of the position of the working class. In addition, the impact of social and economic standard of graduate in North to the developing countries in terms of salary scales, elite lifestyle, and general attitude toward the private accumulation of wealth tend to weaken any meaningful efforts at poverty alleviation. This is because whether there are friendly policies or a well focused government intervention, such attitudes tend to exacerbate the level of corruption and economic plunder by a privileged minority. A good example for Nigeria can be found between the years 1999-2007, the revenue of the Federation was a whopping N27.7 trillion. This amount of money was more than 80 percent of Nigeria Federally collected revenue from 1970-2007. However, this was not translated to employment generation or social amenities provision due to corruption in high places. In fact as observed by Yusufu (2010), the roads and powers sectors were in parlous state across the country regardless of N 500 billion the Federal Government, under President Obasanjo claimed to have invested in those sectors between 1999 and 2002.

Measures to Curb Capitalist Exploitation of Young Graduates in Nigeria

Given the level of dependence, the Nigerian state has adopted many bourgeois-oriented

strategies to explode the shells of backwardness however, the present day Nigeria seems to be taking a leap at mixed economic system due to low impact of socialism to bring about real economic growth and development. Developing countries of which Nigeria is one, are calling on both the government and private sectors to cooperate and develop the country's economy. Recently, the government is adopting the public- private partnership initiative in achieving and accelerating some developmental objectives. Pivoting the economy cannot be left in the hand of the private sector alone; there is the need for the government to participate fully.

On the basis of the perceived strengths of import substitution, the Nigerian state initially placed emphasis on agro-allied industries. This included vegetable oil extraction, tanning, textiles, brewing, and cement manufacturing. But as the economy gained strength due to oil boom of the 1970's, this strategy was extended to light and heavy industries. For instance, the Third Development Plan of 1975-80 emphasized vehicle assembly plants as well as the development of heavy industries such as iron, steel, and petrochemical projects (Uwechue, 1991). However, as oil revenue shrank in the 1980s, manufacturing activity was also reduced drastically. The government was constrained to deemphasize the policy of promoting heavy industries. If put to practice, it will help in eradicating capitalist exploitation of graduates.

Conclusion

The vision of sustainable development can only be attained by generating employment, especially for the graduates of Universities and Polytechnics. Overdependence on the petroleum sector cannot guarantee the required job for the teaming graduates, besides, certain global market forces might lead to a drop in the demand for crude oil and its products in the nearest future. Nigeria should borrow a leaf from other countries, like Germany, which had over three million Small and Medium scale Enterprises built on individual entrepreneurship and the government provides them with the right framework to ensure their success. Also, the higher institutions of learning need to teach graduates employable skills

Recommendations

The establishment of Work Incentive Program (WIN) by the Nigerian State, as is done in the capitalist America Government in league with the private sector. Secondly, Unemployment Insurance Benefits and social security system should be taken into serious consideration in Nigeria, to cover one or two years of graduates, immediately after leaving school.

We also recommend private sector job initiatives and self employment initiatives as remedies to graduate unemployment. Presently, there is a mismatch between higher education, skill set and labor market demand in the country, therefore the education curricular needs to be revised especially at high school and higher education levels.

Finally, these acts of exploitation of the jobless and job-seeking are callous and unpardonable. A jobless person is poor and needs all the money he can muster, to keep body and soul together. Employers should advertise their vacancies in newspapers and accept applications in hard copy (through the post or hand delivery) or through emails, as alternatives to filling online applications forms.

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